

XII Congreso Ibérico de Agroingeniería

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4-6 septiembre 2023

Libro de actas · Livro de atas

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Título: Proceedings of the 12th Iberian Agroengineering Congress.
(Libro de actas del XII Congreso Ibérico de Agroingeniería)
(Livro de atas del XII Congreso Ibérico de Agroengenharia)

Editores: Manuel Pérez Ruiz, Gregorio Egea Cegarra, Luis Pérez Urrestarazu, Isabel Díaz de la Torre, Antonio Rodríguez Lizana, Antonio Franco Salas, Manuel Jesús González Ortega, Rocío Pineda Martos y Alejandro Prior Fernández. Universidad de Sevilla, España.

Publicado: Servicio de Publicaciones de la Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural. Junta de Andalucía

Edita: Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería Agronómica. Universidad de Sevilla.

Impresión: Gandulfo Impresores, S.L.

ISBN: 978-84-09-53018-2

Depósito Legal: SE 1503-2023

1ª Edición. Sevilla, 2023

Establishing a Sustainable and Healthy Local Food System through the Establishment of Urban Spaces within two cities in Spain

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Abstract:

Addressing the food sector in cities has become a topical issue of major importance, particularly in view of continuing population growth. Indeed, this research paper aims to provide empirical findings on the link between Urban Agriculture and Food Security in two Spanish cities. The two initiatives evaluated are “Estrategia Alimentaria de Valladolid” and «Alimenta Conciencia» in Segovia. This work was carried out through interviews with the project managers, which enabled us to find out how the different projects assess local production and its interaction within the cities. Based on the interviews conducted, it emerged that the two initiatives had a number of points in common, such as the desire to ensure that people are properly educated and aware of the value of integrating the food sector into cities, as well as on the proper organization of activities and workshops in, and above all, the encouragement of small organizations and start-ups linked to local production and consumption, as they form the basis of any future project.

Keywords: Urban Agriculture, Food Security, Interviews, Spain

1. Introduction

The United Nations Human Settlements Program [1] has estimated that 60% of the population will reside in urban areas by 2030. This will result in increased pressure on urban resources, particularly in cities in low- and middle-income countries, putting pressure on urban Food Security [2]. In addition, rapid urbanization and industrial agricultural production of food has led to a growing disconnection between urban residents and their food sources [3].

Although Urban Agriculture is increasingly seen by policy makers and urban researchers as a very promising pillar of Food Security, it is also increasingly seen as an essential component of Food Security, and researchers as a very promising pillar of informal food supply systems [4,5], the evidence of its impact on urban Food Security is still very anecdotal and contested. Thornton argued that it has become necessary to discuss the efficiencies of Urban Agriculture to improve the livelihoods of poor urban households [6].

We are in an era of concern for people's mental health and well-being. Indeed, in 2017, and according to the World Health Organization, depression is now the leading cause of ill health and

disability worldwide, with over 300 million people affected [7]. There is a growing realization that connection with nature, which can be reduced in urban environments, is an important contributor to our mental health and well-being [8, 9].

Over the past two decades, Urban Agriculture, which involves growing plants and raising livestock in cities, has attracted increasing interest. Recognized for its potential socio-cultural, public health, environmental and economic development benefits [10], and through initiatives such as the Milan Urban Food Pact, which promotes local food production as a way to address Urban Agriculture, Urban Agriculture has gained increasing interest. Indeed, initiatives such as the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact promote local food production as a way to address the problem of access to fresh food in cities [11].

Urban Agriculture has emerged simultaneously in many cities around the world, colonizing various interstices of the urban scene and adopting different forms and social patterns [4,12]. Indeed, several types of Urban Agriculture can be defined in the European context, such as community gardens, allotments, home gardening in one's own garden or on one's balcony, etc.

Considering the current situation, this study aims to provide empirical findings on the link between Urban Agriculture and Food Security through two Urban Agriculture studies carried out in Spain, in the cities of Valladolid and Segovia. The objective of this paper is therefore to determine the significance of Urban Agriculture in addressing household food insecurity.

2. Methodology

This study adopted the conceptual framework of Gamhewage et al., and illustrated in Figure 1 [13]. However, the decision to participate in Urban Agriculture is affected by three categories of factors. These include socio-economic factors, perception of Urban Agriculture and constraints that hinder efforts to participate (Figure 1). Socio-economic factors influence the availability of resources such as human resources, time, investment, access to land (space for Urban Agriculture) and practical knowledge of Urban Agriculture. Socio-economic factors are influenced by demographic characteristics, livelihood characteristics and capacity characteristics [14].

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for participation in Urban Agricultural practices (Source: Gamhewage et al. 2015).

Qualitative methodology was chosen to investigate the subjective experiences of the program participants because it allows for exploratory enquiry, clarification of ambiguities, discovery of unanticipated findings and information- rich material to enable a deep understanding of the phenomenon under investigation [15].

2.1. Interviews

This paper draws from semi-structured interviews, participant observation, and discourse analysis of public documents during the month of May 2022. Indeed, in-depth interviews were conducted at with project managers of three initiatives to better understand changes that may have occurred in gardeners' lives during their implementation within those initiatives as well as their experiences and techniques in a collective learning process, by talking, sending messages through social networks or merely observing. However, to make the analysis clearer and concrete, we conducted and analysed field observations.

2.2. Content of the interviews

Several questions were posed to examine perceptions of how gardens influenced social capital and Food Security. Furthermore, our interviewees were asked about what they considered to be the key successes and challenges related to the community garden projects they are involved in. Indeed, we selected 3 initiatives of including urban agricultural practices in their planning, representative of the different typologies identified in the preliminary inventory, to develop in-depth interviews and field visits. Third, we conducted and analysed interviews and field.

We asked gardeners to identify benefits provided at individual. Examples of questions may include: What are the objectives of your initiative, if you could describe them in your own words? What kind of activities/tasks are you organizing or doing at the moment? What is the main lesson you personally have learned so far from your work on Food Security and urban inclusion in this project? As well as other questions related to the neighbourhood, the contribution to the city itself and on the identified benefits of the project.

Interviews conducted were recorded in Spanish, and later professionally transcribed into English for analysis using a transcription service and verification from an expert. Moreover, the interviews were conducted in two modalities: in person and online through the Teams software.

3. Results

By carrying out interviews with the project managers of the two initiatives, "Alimenta Conciencia de Segovia" and "Estrategia Alimentaria de Valladolid", we were able to obtain a considerable amount of information about the two projects and about the current situation in Spain, as well as gathering, through their own statements, information about the activities carried out, the objectives they would like to achieve and the obstacles they are encountering.

The following sections illustrate the previous points in further detail, enabling us to gain a better understanding of each of the two initiatives and to draw appropriate and relevant conclusions.

3.1. «Alimenta Conciencia» In Segovia

3.1.1. Presentation and objectives

Segovia is an active city in terms of health and equity, education, and participation. To achieve a sustainable and healthy food system, Segovia's sustainable food strategy has the objectives of coordinating between the different administrations and promoting better administrative coordination.

The main objectives of this initiative are to better know what is produced and consumed and how they affect the local economy and depopulation, as well as promoting a more sustainable, local, healthy, and seasonal diet.

The interview was conducted with Ana Teresa López Pastor, coordinator of the «Alimenta Conciencia» project. With the aim of combating food insecurity and promoting awareness, this innovative initiative was launched in 2019. However, due to the far-reaching effects of the Covid-19 pandemic, the expected timeframe for completion of the project has been postponed from 2022 to the end of 2023. This delay was imposed due to major unexpected challenges posed by the pandemic, such as limited access to resources, restricted supply chains and the necessity to adjust project activities to ensure the safety of the participants.

According to the interviews done with Ana Teresa, her motivations about this project are the following: "I am aware of the importance of food in this area", which means to ensure a sustainable development; and: "I have a conception of the university academy as an information transfer", which means to contribute as much as possible to a better world for all.

These challenging objectives are being achieved through a carefully designed framework, consisting of four key steps:

Collaboration and Cooperation:

With all social actors involved in the project. Recognizing that the success of such an initiative depends on collective efforts, Ana Teresa stresses that meaningful engagement and partnerships are essential to the global impact of the project.

Moreover, in their opinion, without strong cooperation and collaboration, the project's objectives would be ineffective and the potential impact would be diminished. By building a network of interconnected social actors, projects can leverage collective knowledge, pool resources, and create synergies beyond individual efforts.

Increase organic production: Ana Teresa López Pastor envisions the future of the «Alimenta Conciencia» project, oriented towards organic farming. Organic farming offers many benefits, including environmental sustainability, improved soil regeneration and the production of healthier food for consumers.

Consumption: Ana Teresa explained an important aspect of the Alimenta Conciencia project: local consumption, while encouraging citizens to give priority to products grown in the city or nearby, known as "Segovia Eco Kilo 0". Emphasize the purpose of increasing. In fact, there are many benefits to encouraging citizens to consume local products. First, it supports the local economy by directly contributing to the livelihoods of local farmers and producers, sustaining rural communities, and creating jobs.

Communication and education: fundamental aspects of the «Alimenta Conciencia» project. Indeed, the project aims to raise awareness and encourage people to adopt sustainable practices, ensuring a more sustainable and healthier future for current and future generations. Indeed, various educational and educational activities such as school workshops and programs about building sustainable local food systems are realized.

3.1.2. Current steps and activities in line with the project

The city of Segovia is deeply involved in a series of actions and activities that are aligned with the objectives of the «Alimenta Conciencia» project. These initiatives aim to promote a sustainable and healthy food system in and around the city (Table 1).

Table 1. Actions and activities developed by «Alimenta Conciencia» – Segovia City

	Actions and activities
1	3 local stores in Segovia
2	Working on sustainable gastronomic tourism
3	Working with restaurants
4	Organizing several awareness raising activities
5	Explore the distribution opportunities to develop food products
6	Working with students on Food Security and sustainable development projects

Table 1 clearly shows that the «Alimenta Conciencia» project aims to implement measures and activities to ensure a more sustainable and healthier food system. This was achieved by establishing three local shops in Segovia, which encouraged farmers in the province to sell their local produce in these shops and encouraged consumers to go to other markets. Indeed, we are striving to According to Ana Teresa, it is necessary to carry out many educational activities to students to clarify the importance of local healthy food.

3.1.2. Main challenges and problems faced

The main challenge «Alimenta Conciencia» wants to ensure is mainly to share more knowledge and a more positive attitude towards these food systems. Another very important aspect is to change the way of consumption, switching to the consumption of local and neighborhood products (Segovia Eco Km0) instead of buying products in non-local stores outside the city.

Regarding the problems encountered during the project, Ana Teresa emphasized the lack of economic resources, which is above all a problem in driving action, but at the same time the lack of participants, people usually stressed that although they wanted to participate, they did not necessarily participate actively.

Finally, Ana Teresa highlighted another aspect related to the war in Ukraine. In fact, she acknowledged, this has caused a global food crisis and led to higher product prices. Today, however, it is necessary to create a healthy and comfortable environment in order to provide people with local products.

3.2. «Estrategia Alimentaria de Valladolid»

3.2.1. Presentation and objectives

The city of Valladolid has developed a process of reflection on the local agri-food system. This process of research and reflection has led to a participatory process for drafting a Food Strategy for the city, which will then be translated into an action plan. At the same time, the strategy has begun its implementation phase, which is currently underway.

This project was launched by the City Council of Valladolid, the Fondation Entretantos and the University of Valladolid.

The principal objective of the project is to promote a space for collective transformation of the food system, work with other sectors for a more prolonged use of processed foods, as well as broadening the sales channels, opening a niche in collective catering and even the possibility of developing new allergen-free products and innovation. This would generate very positive learning, relationships, and synergies for the local food system.

The interview was done with María Sánchez Esteban, the councilor for the environment and the fourth deputy mayor of the City Council of the city of Valladolid.

Indeed, Maria Sanchez Esteban mentioned that the project started on 2016, and highlighted its main objectives, which are:

- “People who work the land are the local producers of Valladolid and the surrounding area of Castilla y León and can develop their activities in a responsible manner. »; and,

- "People can have access to food close to their homes, without travelling "Km 0".

Furthermore, she highlighted that the city of Valladolid and its surroundings have been developing a process of reflection on the local agri-food system over the last few years so as to start launching a participatory process for the development of a food strategy of its own and ensure new strategies such as "Valladolid's Agri-Food Strategy: participatory process".

3.2.2. Activities organized

Table 2 shows the main activities carried out by the «Estrategia Alimentaria de Valladolid» initiative. in the words of our interviewee Maria Sanchez. She points out that one of the main activities organized is the setting up of local markets. This market will connect the community by showcasing the diversity of the city's products, creating a thriving and dynamic local market for vendors and visitors alike. The second activity highlighted by Maria Sanchez is the planification of educational activities, with the aim of emphasizing the importance of good nutrition.

Table 2. Activities organized by «Estrategia Alimentaria de Valladolid».

Main activities	Explication
Local markets	Organization of a local markets once a month that brings together several local producers in the city of Valladolid.
Pedagogical activities	Organize pedagogical activities within educational systems to ensure a well insertion and participation of children within the importance of eating healthy and locally and to show them how to plant a certain fruit or vegetable
Encourage local consumption	Organize activities and workshops open to the public to explain the importance of eating locally for our health and wellbeing, as well as encourage them to start cultivating their own fruits and vegetable in their gardens and/or balconies etc., if possible.

These activities will enable students to learn more about good nutrition and the positive impact it has on our well-being. To achieve this, several practical exercises are organized, such as practical advice on meat planning from experts, nutritional information and healthy cooking techniques, together with how these can improve our health and our daily lives. The final main activity is to encourage local consumption by supporting local businesses and raising awareness of the benefits of buying local produce. To achieve this, various events are organized, as well as open days and activities, to show local people the positive impact on the environment and its impact on our daily lives (Table 2).

3.2.2. Challenges encountered

According to Table 3, Valladolid City Council plans to set up permanent local markets where farmers can sell their produce to consumers. It will also encourage them to open their own businesses in the city, and to put a stain on a piece of land to make it easier for them to access property and sell their local produce to residents. In addition, the project aims to organise more activities to share knowledge and raise awareness, to highlight the importance of eating locally and to encourage local people to buy from local markets.

Table 3. Main challenges encountered by «Estrategia Alimentaria de Valladolid».

Main challenges	Explication
Implementation of markets	Implement local places for markets that encourage local producers of the city of Valladolid and its surrounding to sell their products.

Share knowledge and awareness	Organize more activities to children to help them to know the importance of eating healthy and locally
Own business	Putting a stain in a land bank so that local producers can take it to their business in Valladolid
Local consumption	That people eat healthy and locally without worrying about the origin of food and if it's healthy or not, and specially, encourage them to buy from the near province, and not going to other cities to by their local products

4. Discussion and conclusion

The involvement of the food sector in cities has become a topical issue of major importance, especially in view of continuing population growth [1]. This research has enabled us to assess the situation in two Spanish cities. The initiatives evaluated were “Estrategia Alimentaria in Valladolid” and «Alimenta Conciencia» in Segovia. In fact, this work enabled us to find out how the various initiatives assess local production and its interaction within the two cities of Valladolid and Segovia.

Based on the interviews carried out, it emerged that the two initiatives had several points in common. Indeed, both projects are willing to ensure that people are properly educated and aware of the value of integrating the food sector into cities, we need to organize more and more activities and workshops along these lines [16]. In addition, small organizations and start-ups need to be supported, as they are the foundation of any future project [17].

Both initiatives also confirmed that there is a lack of local production and sales in the two cities of Segovia and Valladolid because farmers don't have their own premises, so one of the fundamental actions that needs to be taken is to encourage them to open their own premises and sell their products to residents, instead of having to travel to another city [18].

A very important point also mentioned was to ensure good urban planning by experts. This means that several factors need to be taken into account to achieve this, such as knowing the history and origin of the area to be treated, checking and respecting the right space indicators to implement these urban practices, evaluating the productivity and space required for this, checking all environmental aspects such as soil type, water availability etc., before starting the management of the land, as well as assessing the economic contribution of involving such projects, from the point of view of feasibility and job creation for job seekers, together with a recreational and social integration venue.

Finally, a very important point cited by the initiatives surveyed was the economic aspect. Indeed, project funding and financial support are very important when it comes to setting up a project, hence the need for an increasing number of project grants and public calls for project proposals, a feature that is fully endorsed by the initiatives evaluated.

Acknowledgement

The present work is related to FUSILLI Project, which is based on food and natural resources. This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No.101000717. FUSILLI mainly focuses on supporting cities to facilitate their transition to more sustainable food systems, in accordance with FOOD2030 priorities. <https://fusilli-project.eu/>

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